

**DEVELOPMENT OF LEARNING MANAGEMENT PROCESSES
BASED ON THE CONTEMPLATIVE EDUCATION AND THE
OPTIMUM EXPERIENCE APPROACHES FOR LEADING OF
OPTIMUM LEARNING QUALITY TOWARD TEACHER-EARLY
CHILDHOOD INTERACTIONAL RELATIONSHIPS**

**Jariyaporn Sakulprahm¹,
Pattamasiri Teeranurak Jaruchainiwat²,
Charinee Triwaranyu³**

^{1,2,3}Department of Curriculum and Instruction, Faculty of Education, Chulalongkorn University,
254 Phayathai Road, Pathumwan Bangkok, Thailand, 10330

Abstract:

To develop learning management process based on the *Contemplative Education Approach* (CEA) and the *Optimum Experience Approach* (OEA) to enhance the ability relationships between teachers and students were built up, students' responses of their effects to their learning management process based on the CEA and OEA towards teacher and Early childhoods were respected, such as, being lovely, affectively children, and creating conduction to their classroom learning environments. To administer which as 165 early childhood students in 11 classes and 11 teachers from the Early Childhood School at Bang Sai Royal Folk Arts and Crafts Center under the Royal Patronage of Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn were participated with the qualitative data, collectively. Research procedures were designed in 2 steps; first, teachers plans to manage the instructional design for including early childhoods who ought to practice their experiences and self-learning processes on self-awareness with practicing mindfulness through their self-observing activities, to improve the meditational activities and real life with themselves were observed by teachers, second, early childhoods respective learning of their opportunity on modern experience, self-literacy, self-mindfulness observation, observing a case study on their activities, and self-practicing daily life. Most of teachers were able to invent and change the increasing relationships between teachers and early childhoods' abilities evidence from 1 to 2 scales. Relationships between teachers and students were invented the instructional

processes with the role models' teaching management to support and create children' learning activities, children' learning outcomes of their understanding, self-awareness, learning abilities, and were responded by teachers' interaction behaviours with the CEA and OEA instructional methods to their classroom environments. Based on the findings, suggestions for enhancing teachers' and children' abilities of their associations between the CEA and OEA classroom environments are needs. The developing learning management processes are explored, respected, accepted, and loved ties for children, relatively.

Keywords: development, learning management processes, contemplative education approach, optimum experience approach, enhancing abilities, teacher-early childhood interactional relationships

Introduction

Education in Thailand is provided mainly by the Thai government through the Ministry of Education from pre-school to senior high school. A free basic education of twelve years is guaranteed by the constitution, and a minimum of nine years' school attendance is mandatory (Ministry of Education, 2016). In 2009 the Ministry of Education announced the extension of a free, mandatory education to fifteen years. Formal education consists of at least twelve years of basic education, and higher education. Basic education is divided into six years of elementary education and six years of secondary education, the latter being further divided into three years of lower- and upper-secondary levels (World Education News & Reviews, 2014). Kindergarten levels of pre-elementary education, also part of the basic education level, span 2–3 years depending on the locale, and are variably provided. Non-formal education is also supported by the state. Independent schools contribute significantly to the general education infrastructure. Formal education consists of at least twelve years of basic education, and higher education. Basic education is divided into six years of elementary education and six years of secondary education, the latter being further divided into three years of lower- and upper-secondary levels. Kindergarten levels of pre-elementary education, also part of the basic education level, span 2–3 years depending on the locale, and are variably provided. Non-formal education is also supported by the state. Independent schools contribute significantly to the general education infrastructure (World Education News & Reviews, 2014). This research study would be selected for the sample size consisted of the pre-elementary education.

Learning development describes work with students and staff to develop academic practices, with a main focus on students developing academic practices in educational system. Learning developers are academic professionals who teach, advise and facilitate students to develop their academic practices; create academic development learning resources; and reflect on their own academic practices through a community of practice (Association for Learning Development in Education, 2012). Hilsdon (2011) defines Learning Development (L&D) as a complex set of multi-disciplinary and cross-disciplinary academic roles and functions, involving teaching, tutoring, research, and the design and production of learning materials, as well as involvement in staff development, policy-making and other consultative activities. In this study, researcher team will remain the development of Early childhoods learning achievement movement to begin with the recognition of a new direction of practice emerging by early childhood teachers and their Early childhoods in the early members with the Contemplative Education Approach (CEA) and the Optimum Experience Approach (OEA) instructional methods.

Generally, the *Contemplative Education* is a philosophy of higher education that integrates introspection and experiential learning into academic study in order to support academic and social engagement, develops self-understanding as well as analytical and critical capacities, and cultivates skills for engaging constructively with others (Lewis, 2006). The inclusion of contemplative and introspective practices in academia addresses an increasingly recognized imbalance in educational level: a lack of support for developing purpose and meaning, or for helping students “*learn who they are, search for larger purpose for their lives, and leave schools as better human beings*” (Hart, 2004). While contemplative education aims to integrate contemplative practices and perspectives within any subject of study, the discipline of contemplative studies; the examination of the contemplative experience itself has also developed (Hodes, 2014). Thus, the contemplative education is defined as a set of practices that may foster particular forms of awareness in students, forms conducive to the conscious motivation and regulation of learning, and also to freedom and transcendence in life more generally (Roeser and Peck, 2009).

This current study focused on pre-elementary educational school classes of education aims to develop the contemplative approaches to significantly improve Early childhoods Pre-K through 4 teacher education and to address other critical challenges in instructional learning management processes based on the CEA based in contemplative practices, such as; their experiences and self-learning processes on self-awareness with practicing mindfulness through their self-observing activities, to improve the

meditational activities and real life with themselves were observed by teachers. Early childhood's respective learning of their opportunity on modern experience, self-literacy, self-mindfulness observation, observing a case study on their activities, and self-practicing daily life, and mindfulness for effects on child well-being and performance were related abilities.

In the last two decades, a large number of studies conducted to show that optimum experience approach (OEA) is a positive and complex condition in which cognitive, motivational and emotional components coexist in a coherent and articulated reciprocal integration (Fave, 2009). Optimum experience thinking is the mental technology that empowers someone who ought to have the best thinking and to be able to stop itself with the realistic thinking style, making the most constructive choices, and take the best actions to accomplish the highest priorities (Covey, 1998). By virtue of its positive psychological features, optimal experience has been sometimes misunderstood as a state which automatically brings about well-being and development. Several studies have disconfirmed this assumption, showing that the outcomes of optimal experience are not automatically positive (Fave, 2009). Rather, the OEA is varying according to the features of the associated activities and to the value system of the cultural environment.

Researcher team of this current study has been primarily devoted the attention to the structure of the activities that promote the OEA, and to the goal pursuit facilitate. Goals are given a prominent role in development in that evidence of four training teachers provide individuals with practical orientation and purpose in children's daily life. This research framework was developed learning management processes for enhancing teachers' and children's relatively abilities in their OEA learning classroom environments. Early childhoods might be responded on the questions that followed as: What does research team know about the relationships between the OEA and teacher-child making self-ego without self-defences? How teachers and their early childhoods were participated to attention, perfectly? What does the situation lead to optimum learning experiences? These research questions are answered to seek Teacher-Early Childhood Interactional Relationships with research study, interestingly.

Research Objectives

1. To develop the learning management processes based on contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for leading

optimum learning quality toward teacher-early childhood interactional relationships.

2. To investigate of the using results of the learning management processes based on contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for leading optimum learning quality toward teacher-early childhood interactional relationships which the affecting interpersonal teachers on their early childhoods' accepting respect, love ties, and contributing classroom environment inventories.

Methodology

Research Framework

According to the thinking theory of Grossenbacher and Parkin (2006) who describes of the Contemplative education challenges and supports students in ways that greatly expand upon traditional academic approaches. This innovative form of education equips students with perspectives and techniques useful for bringing forth their own genuine way of connecting their heart and mind. The theory of Chano (2012) details on contemplative education as learning infused with the experience of awareness, insight and compassion for oneself and others honed through the practice of sitting meditation and other contemplative disciplines.

Figure 1: The Contemplative Educational thinking theory of Grossenbacher and Parkin (2006)

This research procedure is following as the thinking theory of Michael Mendizza and Joseph Chilton Pearce (2003) helps early childhoods rediscover the playful, childlike genius of their own nature as they guide, learn from and mentor children. Discovering and exploring this fresh creative energy transforms the children, which results in radically different learning environments for children. Changing the Early childhoods change the environment, its called childhood, this transforms the child. When early childhoods mirror this new creative energy it cycles back and transforms the adult, it's called this playful, reciprocal dynamic, the *Optimum Learning Relationship*. Capability building, which is central to organizational performance, requires a systematic management approach to learning and development as an integral part of workforce planning.

Sample Size

To administer which a sample size consisted of 165 early childhood students in 11 classes and 11 teachers who were trained by the learning management processes based on contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for their instructional methods from the Early Childhood School at Bang Sai Royal Folk Arts And Crafts Center under the Royal Patronage of Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn were participated with the qualitative data with the purposive random sampling technique, collectively.

Research Procedures

This study developed of learning management processing introduction on the fundamental elements of a qualitative approach to research, which the processes ought to help research team to understand and become proficient in the qualitative methods discussed in subsequent data. The research procedures were recommended to consult the qualitative research in five steps that following as:

Step I: Preparation

R0: What were the components and properties of the frameworks on the instructional processes with based on the contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for leading optimum learning quality toward teacher-early childhood interactional relationships?

Step II: Learning Management of Building Processes

To build up the learning management processes for training teachers' thinking whose know what a learning management processes are. The problems are that teachers make sense of all thinking different things. Is it a learning portal? What does a training record system of teachers' observation to their children? How about teachers use the instructional tools? Are the Contemplative Education Approach (CEA) and the Optimum Experience Approach (OEA) the valid and reliable, significant? What are associations between the relationships of teachers and early childhoods in the virtual CEA and OEA classroom learning environments? These answers are that they could be all of these things to be called '*Learning Management of Building Processes*' which planed for leading to highest learning potential (D1R1) with the CEA and OEA were assessed.

D1: The original instructional learning managements are followed as the approaching theory of the Contemplative Education Approach (CEA) and the Optimum Experience Approach (OEA).

R1: How many steps are there the instructional learning management approaches of the learning activities and processes with the CEA and the OEA?

Step III: Developing Learning Management Processes for the First Phase

Underpinning the learning management process is a new set of knowledge and skills, collectively referred to as a futures orientation and which attempt to prepare the mindsets and skill sets of teaching graduates for conditions of early childhood's changes. The practitioner of learning management is referred to as a learning manager was developed by teachers (D2R2).

D2: To develop the learning management processes with the CEA and the OEA are improved in the first phase.

R2: What are the barriers' using of the CEA and the OEA?

Step IV: Developing Learning Management Processes for the Second Phase

Adjust to the theory and practice of learning management process is develop the Learning Management Design Process (LMDP). The LMDP is a curriculum planning process comprising 'learning design based' questions. This process was developed and used primarily as a tool to train teachers to teach. These questions are answered in sequence focus the teacher to what is important when planning to teach early childhoods (D3R3).

D2: To develop the designing learning management processes with the CEA and the OEA are improved in the second phase.

R2: What are the barriers' using of the CEA and the OEA able to develop the teachers' abilities for building up the relationships between teachers and their early childhoods?

Step V: Presentation of the Learning Management Processes

The CEA and the OEA were organized through the sequential phases: Outcomes, Strategy and Evidence. Each phase represents the development of information that its associated questions seeks to pursue. The CEA and the OEA classroom learning environments represent a rethink of the various curriculum development texts that have predominated the planning of teaching and curriculum in the developing early childhood, completely. The teachers develop their '*teaching plan*' by engaging with each phase and its questions and recording '*findings*' (or answers, observation, and others) in planning activities related forms (D4).

Finally, in this recent research study, using the framework thinking theories to build up the relationships between teacher interactional or interpersonal behaviours to their early childhoods which for leading optimum quality of children with the seven relative interactional prototypes, namely; self-respective associations between teachers and children, safety leaning activities, open-endedness unexpected, observing children signals, deeply and completely responsibilities, imagine and insight, and renewing of early childhoods learning optimum qualities.

Results

The results from the qualitative data indicated that a sample size consisted of 165 early childhood students in 11 classes and 11 teachers who were trained by the learning management processes based on contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for their instructional methods from the Early Childhood School at Bang Sai Royal Folk Arts And Crafts Center under the Royal Patronage of Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn were participated with the qualitative data with the purposive random sampling technique, collectively. Most of children were responded of their seven relative interactional prototypes, namely; self-respective associations between teachers and children, safety leaning activities, open-endedness unexpected, observing children signals, deeply and completely responsibilities, imagine and insight, and renewing of early childhoods learning optimum qualities. Developments of the learning management processes based on contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for leading optimum

learning quality on teacher-early childhood interactional relationships were assessed. The findings of this study, which were reported under the two main researcher objectives, are provided.

In terms of the characteristics of associations between teachers and early childhood students were built up of the relative learning management processes based on contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for leading optimum learning quality toward teacher-early childhood interactions in five scales, such as; accepting respects of the children, love ties, and classroom learning environments for contributing learning of children. There are five discipline factors for supporting the learning management processes, such as; self-understanding to leading of self-thinking and well done behaviours are changed, self-training teachers to their conscious awareness on thinking, emotion, and feeling to inhibit responsibility might be changed for looking for children, self-training deeply listening and observing children's deeply out understanding, opportunity disciplines of interactional behaviors between self-talking on the good climate and deeply trust of teachers to children's responses, and connecting knowledge discipline to the life style and teachers' work and meaningful quality for helping children of their real life.

The leaning content of this management processes are separated on three parts, followed as; nature and individual human differences, individualization between children personality, and associations between teachers and children are built, appropriately. The main learning management processes composed with the two phases; first, self-learning for receiving modernization of their life and self-training understanding knowledge; and self-training knowingly, such as; self-training observation on respective activities and daily life; second, learning management processes for children, to receive a new experience for understanding on children, self-training awareness for children with the training observational respect and life styles of children.

Conclusions

There are two general types of qualitative and quantitative data of the research findings for developing learning management processes based on contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach for leading optimum learning quality toward teacher and early childhood interactional relationships were investigated.

Discovering Quantitative Data

Quantitative research gathers data in numerical form which can be put into categories, in units of measurement of this research study. This type of data can be used to construct the background participating memberships of raw data. The quantitative data was discovered on the abilities of relationships between teachers and children interactions for leading of the teachers' changes to their children were composed evidence of:

A. Respective and Acceptance on Children

Qualitative data gathers information, which as open-endedness, observations, interviews, or group discussions to descriptive important was discovered as:

Firstly: There are 11 early childhood teachers who were the participating research memberships to develop the relationships between teachers and children to children' responses indicated that the four teachers were developed of their teaching evidence of only one level, seven teachers who developed of their teaching evidence of two level, increasingly. In term of love ties, only one developing level, there are five teachers were increased and six teachers were able to develop of their teaching with the CEA and OEA learning approaches in the second level.

Secondly: Contributing classroom learning environment inventory with the CEA and OEA learning approaches, there are the numbers of teachers participating research memberships to develop the relationships between teachers and children to children' responses indicated that teachers' developing their teaching evidence of 3, 7, and 1 teachers of their increasing management processes at the 1, 2, and three steps, consequently.

Overall teachers were able to change their abilities to their inventory relationships between teacher interpersonal teaching behaviors and their children toward the differently instructional plans of the CEA and OEA learning approaches. In terms of the teaching abilities background of teachers, previous research study showed that only a few teachers who are able to have their teaching abilities. After they have spent time for using the CEA and OEA learning approaches in one year, they changed the increasing teaching styles with their colleagues on the contributing classroom learning environment inventories of children knowledge, respective and acceptance children, and love ties, consequently. Therefore, the backgrounds of educational quality of teachers were not affected differences, significantly.

B. Discovering Qualitative Data

Using CEA and OEA learning approaches were collected data of the qualitative research to discover on the abilities of relationships between teachers and children interactions for leading of the teachers' changes to their children were composed evidence of:

Self-Developing Teachers' Instructional Lesson Plans

Teachers must be detailed description in teaching plans of their instruction for a lesson that it was develop the learning management processes based on the CEA and the OEA learning approaches for leading optimum of children' learning qualities toward teacher and early childhood interactional relationships with the self-developing teachers' instructional lesson plan. A daily lesson plan is developed by a teacher to guide class learning. Details will vary depending on the preference of the teacher, subject being covered, and the needs of the students. There may be requirements mandated by the school system regarding the plan to include the goal that it will be reached to the instructional procedure with the CEA and the OEA learning approaches. The research findings: Each teacher was developed their abilities for building up the relationships between teacher interactional behaviours of his/her children, differently. Most of teachers ought to change their thinking at the first, understanding of group colleagues, to be explored to their children, consequently. The properties on teacher interpersonal behaviours might be having open-mindedness, too high responsibility, self-attending seriously and continuing of their personality development.

In terms of the outdoor effects, the explicit instructional school policy is a more important of the developing teachers' abilities. The developing teachers' abilities may be managed, seriously and their responses should be made sense of their faith and courage to the school' policy for enhance teachers' instructional design with the CEA and the OEA learning approaches, successfully. Self-nervousness of their private matter was not separated operations between their interactional behaviours toward their children's learning performances.

Research Suggestions

Used of Research Processing Suggestions

Using the learning management research for developing attributable the CEA and the OEA learning approaches in school, school administrator, mentors, and workers who should be have more individualization of their thinking, in the other hand, most of them are staying at the same institutional education with the leading of themselves and

to be able to understand of self-developing peace and produce to children' preach by their parents and schooling memberships, absolutely.

In terms of learning management disciplines and positions that based on the specific and profound of the contemplative education approach and the optimum experience approach. Using the contemplative education and the optimum experience approaches are believed the foundational contemplative at the first to leading of the optimum leaning achievements with the administration and activate management, previously.

Future Research Suggestions

To investigate of the learning management processes based on contemplative education and the optimum experience approaches' variables of the previous research studies, which the variable effects are missed the concept of the contemplative education and the optimum experience approaches for adapting these approaches to practice and train to early childhood level are provided.

Generally, children's durability of their abilities to their relationships between teacher and children interactional behaviours should be has enough times to spend on planning learning management processes more than 1-2 academic years for making several distinctive contributions to be field of classroom learning environments that they are studied to be carried out of curriculum and instruction context.

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